

Use of Cultured Human Keratinocytes for the Management of a Complex Traumatic Auricular Wound

Hector Abraham Peralta Ruiz¹, Jesús Alexis Martínez Rodríguez², Leonel Lozano Lugo³

¹Third-year General Surgery Resident, Mexican Social Security Institute, High Specialty Medical Unit No. 71, Torreón, Coahuila.

²Third-year General Surgery Resident, Mexican Social Security Institute, High Specialty Medical Unit No. 71, Torreón, Coahuila.

³Fourth-year General Surgery Resident, Mexican Social Security Institute, High Specialty Medical Unit No. 71, Torreón, Coahuila.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Complex traumatic injuries of the external ear that cause devitalization with exposed cartilage which requires advanced treatment, as they can lead to both acute infectious complications and late problems related to deformity. Management of these cases usually requires reconstruction; however, conservative treatment is an option that may preserve function and restore the anterior and lateral contours without increasing risks or complications.

Objective: Present a clinical case describing a novel application of cultured human keratinocytes for the management of a complex auricular wound.

Methods: The clinical case of an 11-year-old female patient is presented. She sustained polytrauma with partial loss of the left auricle, 2 x 1.4 cm of exposed cartilage, and loss of skin continuity of the helix. Primary closure was performed, and keratinocytes were manually collected from the Epifast sheet and applied to the raw wound and exposed area. The aim is to present the procedure and its results in order to disseminate another management option that does not involve surgery.

Results: Findings 2 weeks after the first application of Epifast showed cartilaginous exposure measuring 5 mm in diameter, so Epifast was applied again, achieving complete epithelialization of the exposed auricular cartilage at 5 weeks. At 6 months, epidermal thickening with good scar quality was observed; no complications occurred during follow-up.

Conclusion: Application of keratinocytes promotes granulation tissue formation and re-epithelialization by secreting cytokines that modulate cell proliferation, migration, and differentiation during healing of ear wounds with exposed cartilage.

KEYWORDS: Keratinocytes, Epifast, complex auricular wound, complex traumatic injury, external ear, epithelialization.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
06 April 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

The terms avulsion and amputation are reserved exclusively for an injury that results in a separation from the body. Partial amputation of the external ear describes avulsion of a smaller part of the auricle rather than a deep laceration, as the term was previously used [1]. Severe injuries of the external ear that result in traumatic amputation or devitalization require sophisticated treatment, and successful salvage of amputated external ears has been reported, such as with composite grafts. [2]

Post-traumatic auricular reconstruction represents a major challenge for facial plastic surgeons and requires a broad

understanding of various techniques in order to identify the best treatment for each patient. Successful reconstruction of the external ear after trauma depends on two main factors. The first is vascular patency. The second is the availability of soft-tissue coverage over the reimplanted or harvested cartilage framework. [3]

Anatomy:

The external ear is composed of the auricle and the external auditory canal. The auricle itself arises from the six hillocks surrounding the first pharyngeal cleft during the sixth week of gestation. The fully developed ear is characterized by a series of cartilaginous convolutions that define its normal

Use of Cultured Human Keratinocytes for the Management of a Complex Traumatic Auricular Wound

anatomy (Figure 1). This cartilaginous structure may be 1.0 to 3.0 mm thick and has an elastic composition. This cartilage lies between two thin dermal layers that provide its blood supply. The blood supply to the anterior ear comes from branches of the superficial temporal artery that enter the ear

through the root of the helix. The posterior auricular vessels branch from the external carotid artery and enter posteriorly at the inferior surface of the cavum conchae. The anterior and posterior blood vessels merge to form a plexus in the scaphoid fossa. [4]

Figure 1. Diagram of the anatomy of the main regions of the ear

In a study by Gutiérrez et al., 204 cases of auricular trauma were analyzed. Among the affected anatomic regions, 97 cases involved the helix (43%); 90 cases involved more than one region (42%); in 19 cases the lesion was retroauricular (8.87%); in 6 cases only the lobule was affected (2.8%); and in 2 cases the concha was involved (0.93%). [5]

- Etiology:

The most common etiology of auricular trauma is blunt-force injury, such as injuries sustained in contact sports (wrestling, boxing, mixed martial arts, soccer, or rugby). Other causes include any type of assault involving impact to the ear, traffic accidents, or gunshot wounds. The trauma generates shearing forces that disrupt adherence of the perichondrium to the underlying cartilage, especially in the anterior portion, where the skin is firmly attached to the perichondrium. [6]

- Epidemiology:

In a meta-analysis of 326 injured ears, the most frequent causes were traffic accidents (35.9%), injuries at home (27.6%), and fights (24.5%). Ear injuries caused by fights occur predominantly in men (as victims). Among the published cases, those caused by bites, mainly from humans and dogs, are relatively common (40%) [1].

- Pathophysiology:

Burns of the external ear can lead to both acute infectious complications and late problems due to deformity. Circulatory compromise of the perichondrium, either as a direct result of thermal injury or secondary to edema, decreases vascularity. Contraction of the overlying eschar and increasing edema can further reduce vascularity, with consequent loss of perichondrial viability. The cartilage, even if not fully exposed to air, can become secondarily infected through the wound. Perichondritis will cause chondritis, with consequent loss of auricular cartilage. [7]

- Clinical approach:

In all patients who have sustained trauma to the external ear, serious head and/or neck injury must be assessed first. Otoscopy is important to detect any damage to the auditory canal and/or tympanic membrane. The mechanism of trauma,

possible loss of consciousness, diphtheria vaccination status in cases of skin barrier disruption, possible use of anticoagulant/antithrombotic medications, and known predisposing factors for poor wound healing should all be taken into account. [8]

- Classification of auricular injuries:

The classification scheme begins by determining whether the cartilaginous portion of the ear is injured. Complex injuries involving cartilage may be complete or partial avulsions. Partial avulsions can be further subcategorized into injuries with broad or narrow pedicles. [4]

Initial management:

Prophylactic antibiotic treatment is recommended (ciprofloxacin is the first choice to prevent infection by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*); it is generally necessary after careful wound cleansing. The bacteria most frequently found in the external ear are *Staphylococcus aureus*, organisms from the Enterobacteriaceae group, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Whenever possible, the auricular segment should be reattached; even if necrosis occurs, the final result will not be less aesthetic than that obtained with a wait-and-see approach. The avulsed segment should be wrapped in saline-soaked gauze and then placed on ice until reimplantation. Any tissue loss warrants an otolaryngology/plastic surgery opinion within 24 hours, and within 48 hours in the case of any burned ear. If reconstruction is needed, the goal is to preserve function and restore the anterior and lateral contours. [6]

- Reconstruction:

Reconstruction of the external ear is challenging because of the ear's complex three-dimensional architecture and its cosmetic importance for the patient's psychosocial well-being. There are different surgical treatment modalities, which are assessed individually. Cartilage grafts are often used in reconstruction of larger external ear injuries or tears. Reconstruction may consist of simple wound revision, surgical reconstruction of fibrotic cartilage, or complete ear reconstruction with cartilage grafts and flaps. [8] Generally,

Use of Cultured Human Keratinocytes for the Management of a Complex Traumatic Auricular Wound

only debridement is performed initially, followed by a skin graft as a secondary operation. However, this procedure sometimes leads to cartilage exposure due to external irritation, infection, or chondritis. [9] There are advanced wound-care techniques that encompass technologies other than specialized dressings for closure of acute or chronic wounds that are difficult to manage, such as negative-pressure systems, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, hydrosurgical systems, biodebridement, dermal substitutes, temporary biologics, permanent biologics, temporary synthetics, and permanent synthetics [10].

- Cultured epidermal allograft (EpiFast):

The skin is a complex system in which different cell types interact synergistically. The epidermis is composed mainly of keratinocytes, which form a stratified epithelium with proliferating basal cells in the deepest layer and a relatively impermeable keratinized layer at the surface (stratum corneum). The dermis provides structural integrity, elasticity, and a vascular network that nourishes the skin.

Technological advances in biomaterial manufacturing and cell culture have enabled the production of skin substitutes that have contributed to the treatment of burns, chronic wounds, and congenital skin disorders [11]. Keratinocytes secrete cytokines and extracellular matrix proteins that modulate cell proliferation, migration, and differentiation during skin wound healing. Cytokines such as TGF- α , TGF- β , and PDGF are involved in tissue repair after injury; therefore, application of an in vitro cultured epidermal allograft promotes faster re-epithelialization and granulation tissue formation [12].

Epifast® (Bioskinco S.A. de C.V.) is the first living skin equivalent developed from cultured human epidermal cells placed on a layer of petrolatum gauze. It reduces epithelialization time by up to 50% in lesions caused by burns, ulcers, dermabrasions, donor areas, and other skin conditions, shortens patient recovery time, decreases fibrosis and pain, and protects against infection [10].

Clinical case:

We present the case of an 11-year-old girl with no relevant past medical history, no previous surgeries, and no allergies. She presented to the emergency department after a motor vehicle accident with a diagnosis of polytrauma, including fractures of the femur, tibia, and left fibula, right ocular contusion, a left retroauricular lesion with an avulsive wound of the left external auditory canal and exposed cartilage, and loss of skin continuity of the helix.

Initial management by the emergency department consisted of fluid resuscitation, analgesia, and antibiotic therapy. Primary closure was performed with simple interrupted 3-0 nylon sutures in the helix region.

Results:

Four days after the accident, evaluation by the plastic and reconstructive surgery service was requested. The patient had a dermabrasion with crusting in the right facial area; in the left facial area she had a dermabrasion with partial loss of the left auricle, with 2 x 1.4 cm of cartilaginous exposure and loss of skin continuity of the helix due to the previous closure (Image A). Generous application of an ointment based on neomycin and retinol was indicated on the dermabrasions every 8 hours.

Figure 2: EpiFast patch

Image A): Partial loss of the left auricle with 2 x 1.4 cm of exposed cartilage and loss of skin continuity of the helix.

The following day, the previous sutures were removed. Partial loss of the helix and antihelix was observed, with exposed cartilage in the antihelix and crura, and devitalized tissue was debrided. Using 5-0 nylon, the skin edges were approximated, leaving an area of cartilage exposure measuring approximately 1 x 1 cm. Epifast was placed over the wound with exposed cartilage (Figure 2). The wound was covered for 10 days with chloramphenicol ointment applied

every 8 hours. The patient was discharged for outpatient follow-up with a dual oral antibiotic regimen.

Application method. 1) EpiFast. Figure 2. 2) Keratinocyte collection (manual scraping of the petrolatum-gauze backing was performed). Figure 3. 3) Direct application of keratinocytes onto the raw wound (material obtained by scraping EpiFast was placed onto the wound with tissue forceps; approximate diameter of cartilage exposure, 0.5 cm). Figure 4. 4) Placement of petrolatum gauze (Jelonet) over the

Use of Cultured Human Keratinocytes for the Management of a Complex Traumatic Auricular Wound

keratinocytes and the wound (one full gauze was placed with four folds).Figure 5.

Figure 3: Start of application in the injury

Figure 4: Application with forceps

Use of Cultured Human Keratinocytes for the Management of a Complex Traumatic Auricular Wound

Figure 5: Placement of petrolatum

At the 2-week follow-up visit, decreased cartilaginous exposure was observed, measuring 5 mm in diameter, with irregularity of the helix (Image B). Wound care was performed with suture removal, Epifast was placed on the area of exposed cartilage, and the conservative closure process was continued.

Image B): Approximately 5 mm diameter area of exposed cartilage.

At the subsequent visit 2 months later, following application of Epifast, the patient showed epithelialization of the auricular cartilage and a thin epidermal layer with a notch in the helix (Image C). Hypertrophic scarring was present in the left submandibular region and the left retroauricular region. Management with pressure therapy and vitamin E application to the scars was indicated.

Image C): Thin epithelialized layer over the auricular cartilage.

At 5 months of follow-up, thickening of the epidermis was observed, with good scar quality; a deformity due to scar retraction was noted in the helix (Image D). During follow-up, no complications occurred in the area of exposed cartilage.

Image D): Thickening of the epidermis, with good scar quality.

DISCUSSION

Burns of the auricle continue to carry a high rate of infectious complications; approximately 10% of cases progress to chondritis [13], and the most common pathogen is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which penetrates the epithelium and invades the underlying soft tissue and the perichondrium [6]. This frequently leads to destruction of unburned cartilage, thereby destroying the shape of the ear. It occurs in 5-25% of ear burns and may develop after either total or partial burns; it often occurs after a very superficial injury. [14]

A study from Italy reports that the incidence of infection decreased by 11% with the use of chlorhexidine as an antiseptic dressing. In addition to reducing perilesional edema, it has strong antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. [13]

The importance of performing an appropriate approach in these cases lies in preventing complications. Although surgical procedures were initially performed, we concluded that conservative management could be more beneficial for this patient because of her age, reducing hospital length of stay. This may help reduce a stressful experience that could trigger future psychological reactions in pediatric patients. Since no complications occurred after this complex auricular trauma, we consider it a safe and effective alternative in selected cases.

CONCLUSIONS

Application of keratinocytes (Epifast) promotes granulation tissue formation and re-epithelialization by secreting cytokines that modulate cell proliferation, migration, and differentiation during healing of ear wounds with exposed cartilage.

At present, there is no specific conservative treatment for complex auricular trauma with exposed cartilage. Treatment is individualized; by minimizing the need for autologous grafts and reducing healing time, Epifast optimizes functional and aesthetic outcomes while decreasing donor-site morbidity. Therefore, its integration into reconstructive

protocols represents a significant advance in the pursuit of less invasive, more precise techniques with better long-term results.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest. This article was not funded by Epifast.

REFERENCES

- I. Steffen A, Frenzel H. Trauma management of the auricle. *Facial Plast Surg.* 2015;31(4):382–5.
- II. Turpin IM, Altman DI, Cruz HG, Achauer BM. Salvage of the severely injured ear. *Ann Plast Surg.* 1988;21(2):170–9.
- III. Habiba NU, Khan AH, Khurram MF, Khan MK. Treatment options for partial auricle reconstruction: a prospective study of outcomes and patient satisfaction. *J Wound Car.* 2018;27(9):564–72.
- IV. Lavasani L, Leventhal D, Constantinides M, Krein H. Management of acute soft tissue injury to the auricle. *Facial Plast Surg.* 2010;26(6):445–50.
- V. Gutiérrez GC, Pradel MJJ, Pierdant LR, Lorenzana SC. Estudio epidemiológico del trauma de pabellón auricular en el Hospital General Dr. Manuel Gea González, México. *Cir. plást. iberolatinoam.* 2018; 44(3): 287-295.
- VI. Thill M-P, Horoi M, Ostermann K, Depuydt C, Deschamps M, Ducène C. Acute external ear lesions: clinical aspects, assessment and management. *B-ENT.* 2016;Suppl 26(1):155–71.
- VII. Goel TK, Law EJ, MacMillan BG. Management of the acutely burned ear. *Burns.* 1983;9(3):218–23.
- VIII. Toft-Nielsen C, Lyneborg N. External ear traumas and their complications. *Ugeskr Laeger.* 2019;181(46).
- IX. Saito T, Yotsuyanagi T, Ezoe K, Ikeda K, Yamauchi M, Arai K, et al. The acute surgical management of injury to the helix and antihelix in patients with large

Use of Cultured Human Keratinocytes for the Management of a Complex Traumatic Auricular Wound

- body surface area burns. *J Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg.* 2009;62(8):1020–4.
- X. Domínguez-Saavedra G, Hernández-Galván JM. Actualización en el manejo de heridas. *Cirugía Plástica.* 2021;31(3):124–36.
- XI. Arenas GCM, Merizalde SGJ, Restrepo MLM. Sustitutos cutáneos desarrollados por ingeniería de tejidos. *Iatreia.* 2012 Jan; 25 (1): 5-11.
- XII. Mares MRC, Álvarez TLP, Rosales PJF, et al. Uso de aloinjerto epidérmico cultivado en quemaduras faciales en adultos. *Cir Plast.* 2016;26(3):112-118.
- XIII. Caputo G, Monese C, Governa M, Barisoni D. Letter to the editor: conservative treatment in auricle burns. *Ann Burns Fire Disasters.* 2005;18(4):217–8.
- XIV. Purdue GF, Hunt JL. Chondritis of the burned ear: a preventable complication. *Am J Surg.* 1986;152(3):257–9.